

ARE DISCRIMINATORY TAX RATES ETHICALLY JUSTIFIABLE?

Robert W. McGee¹

JEL Code: D63, H2

Abstract

This paper explores the question of whether discriminatory tax rates are ethically justifiable. The author looks at the issue from various ethical perspectives and concludes that charging different rates to different people cannot be justified on any ethical grounds.

Introduction

A tax system can be structured to have either uniform or discriminatory rates. There are basically three options. One option is a tax that has discriminatory rates. Discriminatory taxes take a larger percentage from some groups than others. An example of a discriminatory system would be a graduated personal income tax, which takes a larger percentage of marginal income from those who earn more, and a lesser percentage from those who earn less. For example, a graduated system might take 10% of taxable income between \$0 and \$10,000; 15% of taxable income between \$10,001 and \$20,000; 25% of taxable income between \$20,001 and \$35,000; and 40% of taxable income over \$35,000. Such a

¹ Seton Hall University. The author would like to thank the two anonymous reviewers for their comments and suggestions. Some of the ideas in this article previously appeared in Robert W. McGee, *Some Tax Advice for Latvia and Other Similarly Situated Emerging Economies*, 13 INTERNATIONAL TAX & BUSINESS LAWYER 223-308 (1996). The author can be reached at bob@dumontinst.com.

system can be complex, with 10 or more different rates, depending on income level; or it can be relatively simple, with just two or three rates.

The second option is a tax that has uniform rates. An example of a tax having a uniform rate would be the flat rate income tax.² One advantage of the flat tax is that it is very simple to compute. It has only one rate, not several. Everyone pays the same rate. If the flat rate is 10%, then someone with \$10,000 in taxable income will pay \$1,000 and someone with \$1,000,000 in taxable income will pay \$100,000. Thus, the rich will pay more in total than the poor, although they will pay the same percentage.

A third option would be a tax that charges everyone the same amount. An example would be a poll tax or a head tax.³ For example, if the total cost of providing government services in a particular community is \$1,000,000 and there are 10,000 people in the community, then every individual would be assessed a tax of \$100. This form of tax is in keeping with the benefits received principle. Assuming everyone benefits equally from government services, then everyone should pay the same amount without regard to income. Otherwise, there are free riders and parasites.

This form of tax is the closest approximation to a market system. For example, if you go into the store to purchase a loaf of bread, the person behind the counter does not ask you what your income is before quoting a price for the bread. The price you pay for the bread is not based on a percentage of your income. The

² ROBERT E. HALL AND ALVIN RABUSHKA, *THE FLAT TAX* (1985). Since no tax is neutral, any change in tax policy will have winners and losers. For a discussion of this point as applied to the flat tax, see Murray N. Rothbard, *The Case Against the Flat Tax* 342-62, in *THE FREE MARKET READER* (LLEWELLYN H. ROCKWELL, ED. 1988). Many taxes that purport to be flat are not really flat because they have exemptions for those whose income falls below some level. These taxes are really graduated because they charge different rates for different levels of income -- 0% for those whose income falls below some minimum and more than zero percent for those whose income is higher than some minimum.

³ J.G. Cullis, P. R. Jones and O. Morrissey, *Public Choice Perspectives on the Poll Tax*, 101 *ECONOMIC JOURNAL* 600-614 (1991).

price is the same for everyone regardless of income level.⁴ And so it is with the poll tax. But the poll tax is not neutral because some people benefit from government services more than others. And if everyone received \$100 worth of services in exchange for a \$100 poll tax, why have a tax in the first place? Why not just abolish taxation and eliminate the middleman (government) by letting individuals pay for the services directly?

While a poll tax may be the fairest of the three options, historically, trying to impose a poll tax has resulted in problems. Margaret Thatcher tried to impose a poll tax in England and triggered vehement public reaction. Those who would have to pay more under a poll tax scheme protested loudly (and sometimes violently). Part of the problem was that the poll tax is a direct tax, and it is visible, not hidden, so people knew exactly what they were paying. When the total cost of the tax is hidden, people do not realize what they are really paying, so there is less of a probability that they will protest. So there appears to be an irreconcilable conflict between fairness and feasibility when it comes to implementing a poll tax, especially if some people (such as the poor, unemployed or retired) cannot afford to pay it.

Ethical Problems with the Graduated Tax

There are basically just two ways to examine an issue from an ethical perspective.⁵ One may take a utilitarian approach or a rights approach. There are several variations of the utilitarian approach, but all utilitarian approaches basically break down to the greatest good for the greatest number.⁶

⁴ I would like to thank Murray N. Rothbard for this example.

⁵ Some authors use more than two categories, but when one breaks down the analysis, one is usually left with some form of utilitarianism.

⁶ For a detailed discussion of utilitarianism, see WILLIAM H. SHAW, *CONTEMPORARY ETHICS: TAKING ACCOUNT OF UTILITARIANISM* (1999). For discussions of the flaws of utilitarianism, see Robert W. McGee, *The Fatal Flaw in the Methodology of Law & Economics*, *COMMENTARIES ON LAW & ECONOMICS* 209-223 (1997); Robert W. McGee, *The Fatal Flaw in NAFTA, GATT and All Other Trade Agreements*, 14 *NORTHWESTERN JOURNAL OF*

Economists are almost all utilitarians.⁷ They consider a policy to be good if it is a positive sum game, if there are more winners than losers. Efficiency and morality are viewed as two sides of the same coin. Something is moral if it is efficient and immoral if it is inefficient.⁸

A graduated tax system discriminates against those who earn more. Such a system is based on the ability to pay principle⁹ rather than the benefits received principle. The benefits received principle is to be preferred to the ability to pay principle, so a graduated tax is less desirable than one that has the same rate for everyone.¹⁰ This is so not only because of fundamental fairness but

INTERNATIONAL LAW & BUSINESS 549-565 (1994); MURRAY N. ROTHBARD, THE ETHICS OF LIBERTY 201-214 (1998); JOHN WILD, PLATO'S MODERN ENEMIES AND THE THEORY OF NATURAL LAW (1953); HENRY B. VEATCH, FOR AN ONTOLOGY OF MORALS: A CRITIQUE OF CONTEMPORARY ETHICAL THEORY (1971); HERBERT SPENCER, SOCIAL STATICS 3-16 (1970). I would like to thank Murray Rothbard for introducing me to some of these sources.

⁷ Some exceptions that come to mind are Walter Block, Murray Rothbard and Hans-Hermann Hoppe.

⁸ RICHARD A. POSNER, ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF LAW, 5TH ED. 284-285 (1998). A variation on the utilitarian theme is the wealth maximization view, which holds that "...the criterion for judging whether acts and institutions are just or good is whether they maximize the wealth of society." RICHARD A. POSNER, THE ECONOMICS OF JUSTICE 115 (1983).

⁹ For a critique of this viewpoint, see Robert W. McGee, *Is the Ability to Pay Principle Ethically Bankrupt?* 1 JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY (Summer 1998).

¹⁰ The ability to pay principle and the benefits received principle are based on two different and conflicting views of government. Under the ability to pay principle, government is viewed as the master and the people as servants. Those who can afford to pay more are forced to pay more. The most productive members of society are exploited, forced to pay for benefits that others receive. They are treated as means, not as ends in themselves. Thus, the ability to pay principle is morally bankrupt.

The benefits received principle is based on the belief that the government is the servant and the people are the masters. Government provides services and people pay for the services through taxes. In an ideal system, people pay for the services they receive and are not forced to pay for services that they do not receive. Of course, the real question, one that is almost

also because it is simpler, and simplicity is to be preferred to complexity.¹¹

Economists have given a number of utilitarian reasons against the graduated income tax as well.¹² For one thing, it destroys the incentive of the most productive people.¹³ And since it is primarily the most productive people who save, invest and create jobs, a graduated tax will retard economic growth by reducing the amount of capital available for investment.

"The most common objection to progressive taxation ... is that it causes an inefficient substitution of leisure for work by increasing the price of work relative to that of leisure."¹⁴ Other objections are that it reduces risk taking,¹⁵ causes wealthy taxpayers to invest in tax schemes to reduce taxes rather than to produce wealth (with the assistance of expensive tax attorneys and accountants),¹⁶ and that it reduces the taxpayer's incentive to allocate resources efficiently, since (some) expenses are deductible. For an individual or corporation in the 40 percent tax bracket, every \$100 expense costs only \$60 after taxes. This

uniformly overlooked, is whether people should be forced to pay for any government services, since, if the services were actually demanded, they could be provided for by the market but better and cheaper, since the market always performs better than government. We will leave discussion of this point for another day.

¹¹ For discussions of tax complexity, see Robert W. McGee, *Taxation and Public Finance: A Philosophical and Ethical Approach*, COMMENTARIES ON THE LAW OF ACCOUNTING & FINANCE 157-240 (1997), at 183-185; James S. Eustice, *Tax Complexity and the Tax Practitioner*, 45 TAX LAW REVIEW 7-24 (Fall 1989); Robert W. McGee, *Is the Internal Revenue Code Void for Vagueness? A Look at Some Economic, Legal and Ethical Issues*, 2 JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY (Fall 1999).

¹² For examples, see WALTER J. BLUM AND HARRY KALVEN, JR., THE UNEASY CASE FOR PROGRESSIVE TAXATION (1953); F.A. Hayek, *The Case Against Progressive Income Taxes*, THE FREEMAN 229-32 (December 28, 1953).

¹³ POSNER, *supra*, at 544-548.

¹⁴ POSNER, *supra*, at 544.

¹⁵ POSNER, *supra*, at 545.

¹⁶ POSNER, *supra*, at 545-546.

argument could be used against both high tax rates in general and graduated tax rates at the higher brackets.

One might argue that it is only fair that the rich pay more in total than the poor, because the rich have more property to protect than the poor.¹⁷ Since protecting property is a function of government, it seems only fair that those who have more property will pay more, in total, for government services than those who own less property. This line of reasoning seems reasonable on the surface. But if one digs beneath the surface, problems start to appear with this line of reasoning. For one thing, there may be little or no relationship between the cost of protecting property and the amount of property to be protected. It may cost more to protect 100 acres of land worth \$10,000 than to protect a bank vault that contains \$100 million.¹⁸ But at least a flat tax makes some attempt at equity, whereas a graduated tax is grounded in the theory of exploitation.¹⁹

Another argument offered in favor of graduated taxes is based on the theory of diminishing marginal utility. According to this theory, taking \$100 from a rich man is not as painful as taking \$100 from a poor man. However, this argument has been totally destroyed by a close examination of the marginal utility theory.²⁰

¹⁷ POSNER, *supra*, at 547.

¹⁸ Murray N. Rothbard makes this point at 115 in *POWER AND MARKET: GOVERNMENT AND THE ECONOMY* (1970).

¹⁹ I am not saying that the graduated income tax should be replaced with a flat tax. There are economic and ethical problems with a flat tax as well. Another option would be to abolish the graduated income tax and replace it with nothing. If government merely got out of the redistribution business and the areas where the market could provide better services there would be no need for any income tax. The federal government functioned quite well without any income tax before 1913. There is no reason to expect that it could not do so again.

²⁰ POSNER, *supra*, at 500-504, 547. One of the problems with the theory is that there is no way to measure interpersonal utilities, so it cannot be determined whether a shift in income from a rich person to a poor person would increase total utility, especially when one takes into account the fact that the rich person knows in advance that the wealth transfer will take place. Rich people may alter

Another advantage of having a single, flat rate is that it does not penalize those who are more productive,²¹ so it does not have as much of an adverse effect on incentives and capital formation (especially if the rate is low). It also does not have as much of an adverse effect on social harmony, since it does not pit one class against another -- the rich against the poor.

Another ethical argument against the graduated income tax is that it pits one class against another -- the rich minority against the poor majority. Thus, it exacerbates class conflict, which no government should do. Governments should represent all of the people, not pit one class against another. Adopting the class conflict philosophy was standard operating procedure for the socialist governments of Eastern Europe, the CIS and China, and for the populist governments of Mussolini, Hitler and Peron. One does not have to do much investigation to see how successful those governments were.

Concluding Comments

Discriminatory tax rates are based on the philosophy of envy and on the discredited view that total utility is increased by taxing a rich person more than a poor person.²² Discriminatory tax rates are based on the philosophy of exploitation, that government is the master and the taxpayers are the servants, who can be exploited. Discriminatory tax rates cannot be ethically justified because they do not treat all taxpayers equally and because the system is economically inefficient. An analysis of the arguments

their behavior to reduce their income and increase their leisure if they feel that they are being exploited. Thus, total wealth is decreased. What does that do to total utility? (Answer: It reduces it.)

²¹ This statement is not quite accurate. It would be more precise to say that the rich are not penalized any more, percentagewise, than the poor. But all groups who earn income are penalized in the sense that a portion of their income is taken from them.

²² Even if it could be proven that taxing a rich man more than a poor man increases total utility, it does not logically follow that it should be done because such a policy is exploitative, and thus morally bankrupt.

for and against graduated tax rates failed to find a single valid argument that could be used to justify discriminatory tax rates, but found several valid arguments against charging different rates to different taxpayers. Thus, discriminatory tax rates are not ethically justifiable under any theory of ethics.²³

²³ Since discriminatory tax rates are ethically bankrupt, one logical question to ask is whether tax evasion might be ethical under a discriminatory tax regime. For more on this point, see ROBERT W. MCGEE, EDITOR, *THE ETHICS OF TAX EVASION* (1998); Robert W. McGee, *Is Tax Evasion Unethical?* 42 *UNIVERSITY OF KANSAS LAW REVIEW* 411-435 (Winter 1994). For authors who take the position that tax evasion is always unethical, see Gordon Cohn, *The Jewish View on Paying Taxes*, 1 *JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY* 109-120 (Spring 1998); Meir Tamari, *Ethical Issues in Tax Evasion: A Jewish Perspective*, 1 *JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY* 121-132 (Spring 1998); Sheldon R. Smith and Kevin C. Kimball, *Tax Evasion and Ethics: A Perspective from Members of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints*, 1 *JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY* (Summer 1998). For a critique of some of these articles, see Robert W. McGee, *Jewish Views on the Ethics of Tax Evasion*, 1 *JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY* (Summer 1998). For a discussion on the justification of taxation generally, see Walter Block, *The Justification for Taxation in the Economics Literature*, in ROBERT W. MCGEE, EDITOR, *THE ETHICS OF TAX EVASION* 36-88 (1998).